

Deriving Euler's Polyhedron Formula from Curvature and Torsion in Metric Space

거리 공간 속 곡률과 꼬임을 통한 오일러의 다면체 공식에 대한 유도

윤지현(Jihyeon Yoon)
somehowme@gmail.com, flyingtext@nate.com
(Amateur Mathematician, Shinhwa Geriatric Hospital)

2024. 7. 20

Abstract

[한글] 거리 공간 속 길이에 대한 정의를 토대로 볼록(convex)의 속성은 정칙 곡선의 일반적인 속성으로 판단할 수 있다. 이를 토대로 곡률과 꼬임의 정도를 결정하는 종법벡터를 나타내는 벡터의 외적이 오일러의 다면체 공식에 의거하여 프레네 삼면체를 형성하는 주요한 근거가 됨을 살펴본다.

[English] The properties convex that is defined in metric space can be regarded as general properties of regular curve. Based on this, the Frenet trihedron described as cross product in binormal vector, grounding for Euler's polyhedron formula.

1 Introduction

All the notations and preconditions follow the book referenced[DC16, Cro16, 김11, FB20, Rud76].

2 Ordinality Defined with Metric Space

It is well-known that metric space is defined with following three properties.

1. $d(p, q) > 0$ if $p \neq q$; $d(p, p) = 0$;
2. $d(p, q) = d(q, p)$;
3. $d(p, q) \leq d(p, r) + d(r, q)$, for $\forall r \in X$.

These properties are defined with three conditions in equivalence of operator.

1. Reflective: $x = x$;
2. Symmetrical: $x = y \Rightarrow y = x$;
3. Transitive: $x = y, y = z \Rightarrow x = z$.

With reflective equivalence, axiom of choice can be introduced. With symmetrical equivalence, commutativity in one from another distance can be set. With transitive equivalence, axiom of order sets.

With no surprise, when metric space exists, ordinality that depends on no number set introduced without any cardinal introduced.

$$\exists d(p, q) \implies \exists \text{ord} \{x : x \in d(\forall p, \forall q)\}$$

This means any set defined that can be metric space has ordinal that can be applied in its intrinsic property.

3 Regular Curve: Convex Defined with Ordinal

It is well known that any convex $E \in \mathbb{R}^k$ follows the form of:

$$x \in E, y \in E, 0 < \lambda < 1 \implies \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y \in E$$

For any normal vector \vec{n} in regular curve which is convex is defined with cross product of binormal vector \vec{b} and tangent vector \vec{t} .

$$\vec{n} = \vec{b} \times \vec{t} = \|\vec{b}\| \|\vec{t}\| \sin \theta$$

So with regular curve, θ with length of vector $\|\vec{n}\|$ controls curvature and torsion, which is well implemented in modern computer graphics editor program. And with ordinality given, any curve as x and y can be used again to define another curve.

$$x, y, x', y' \in E, 0 < \lambda < 1, 0 < \lambda' < 1 \implies \lambda(\lambda'x' + (1 - \lambda')y') + (1 - \lambda)y \in E$$

So although being commutative, ordinality matters in forming curve from curve.

4 Euler's Polyhedron Formula in Cross Product

For determinant in \mathbb{R}^3 :

$$\det(u, v, w) = \begin{vmatrix} u_1 & u_2 & u_3 \\ v_1 & v_2 & v_3 \\ w_1 & w_2 & w_3 \end{vmatrix}$$

Cross product of any vector with orientation follows the form with bases e_1, e_2, e_3 :

$$u \times v = \begin{vmatrix} u_2 & u_3 \\ v_2 & v_3 \end{vmatrix} e_1 - \begin{vmatrix} u_1 & u_3 \\ v_1 & v_3 \end{vmatrix} e_2 + \begin{vmatrix} u_1 & u_2 \\ v_1 & v_2 \end{vmatrix} e_3$$

For three dimensional manifolds, it is well-known as Euler's Polyhedron Formula:

$$v - e + f = 2$$

For determinant variant when set for orientation, number 2 is degree of freedom invariant when one dimension is set for any arbitrary orientation in group representation. For this reason, fixing vertices, edges, and faces differ in their order. This property is derived because Euler characteristics being unit as two-dimensional finite CW-complex. So the orientation become variant in sum of determinants to basis with plus and minus sign.

5 Revisiting Frenet Trihedron as Geodesics

From upper aspects, the Frenet trihedron can be regarded as differentiated basis of geodesic in any manifold.

$$x, y, z \in \text{curvature } E, 0 < \lambda < 1,$$

$$\text{Assuming geodesic in time } T: f(T) = f(x(T), y(T), z(T)) = \lambda x(T) + (1 - \lambda)y(T) + z(T)$$

$$\implies \text{Differentiation of normal vector } (\vec{n})' := (\|\vec{b}\| \|\vec{t}\| \sin \theta)' = -(\text{curvature}) \cdot \vec{t} - (\text{torsion}) \cdot \vec{b},$$

$$\sum_{\forall T} \|\vec{t}\| = \sum_{\forall T} \frac{\|(\vec{n})' + (\text{torsion}) \cdot \vec{b}\|}{(\text{curvature})} = \min_T f$$

$$\implies f - \sum_{\forall T} \frac{\|(\vec{n})' + (\text{torsion}) \cdot \vec{b}\|}{(\text{curvature})} = 0$$

With curvature invariant to orientation, torsion varies over orientation with plus or minus sign, following the degree of freedom in basis of metric space implied with Euler characteristic formula. This provides Frenet trihedron a good reason to be implemented in curvature and torsion as a minimum differentiation unit in geodesics.

References

- [Cro16] Fred H Croom. *Principles of topology*. Courier Dover Publications, 2016.
- [DC16] Manfredo P Do Carmo. *Differential geometry of curves and surfaces: revised and updated second edition*. Courier Dover Publications, 2016.
- [FB20] John B Fraleigh and Neal Brand. *A first course in abstract algebra [rental edition] A first course in abstract algebra [rental edition]*. Pearson, 8 edition, March 2020.
- [Rud76] Walter Rudin. *Principles of mathematical analysis (int'l ed)*. McGraw-Hill Professional, New York, NY, 3 edition, September 1976.
- [김11] 계승혁 김성기, 김도한. *해석개론(개정판 2판)*. September 2011.